

COMPRESSIVE STRENGTH AND DAMAGE MECHANISMS IN STITCHED CARBON/EPOXY COMPOSITES

A. Yudhanto^{1*}, N. Watanabe¹, Y. Iwahori², H. Hoshi²

¹ Department of Aerospace Engineering, Tokyo Metropolitan University, Tokyo, Japan,

² Advanced Composite Technology Center, Japan Aerospace Exploration Agency, Tokyo, Japan

* Corresponding author (yudhanto@sd.tmu.ac.jp)

Keywords: *Stitched composites, compression properties, damage mechanism*

1 Introduction

Impact properties as well as tensile strength of carbon/epoxy composites were found to be improved by through-thickness reinforcement using Vectran[®] stitch thread [1,2]. Schematic of the so-called stitched composites used in Refs. [1,2] is shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Schematic of stitched composites

Because aircraft structures are inevitably subjected to compression loading, the compressive behavior of composites is generally of great importance. When stitched composites are considered as a candidate materials in aircraft structures, a serious concern has particularly been given to their compressive behaviour. Response of stitched composites under compression has been studied for about twenty years, but diverse conclusions were noted. Several researchers found that stitching does not alter compression properties of composites [3-6]. Others found that stitching could improve compression properties [7]. However, in most cases stitching reduces compression strength of up to 55% depending on the type of composite system, stitching parameters and fixtures [8-10]. The

changes of compression properties are related to the failure mechanism: fiber kinking is the principal damage mode, whilst fiber waviness angle is a predominant factor [11-13]. However, no work has been done to describe the actual sequence of compression failure in stitched composites, and thence, the correlation between failure mechanism and compressive strength reduction has not been revealed.

This paper presents an experimental investigation to obtain compressive strength (σ_{uc}) of Vectran-stitched carbon/epoxy composites with varying stitch density and stitch thread thickness. Stitch density and stitch thread thickness (thread diameter) are two important parameters in stitching. Damage mechanisms in unstitched and stitched composites under compression are captured and compared in details.

2 Experimental details

2.1 Materials

Carbon and epoxy used in this experiment are T800SC-24kf and Denatite[®] XNR6813/XNH6813, respectively. Stitch material is Vectran[®] HT. Stitch density (SD ; number of stitch per unit area) is 0.028 mm^{-2} ('stitched 6x6') and 0.111 mm^{-2} ('stitched 3x3'). Stitch thread thickness is 200 denier (200d) and 400 denier (400d). In all, five types of specimens are prepared:

- Unstitched ($SD = 0.0$, $V_s = 0.0\%$)
- Stitched 6x6 200d ($SD = 0.028 \text{ mm}^{-2}$, $V_s = 0.088\%$)
- Stitched 6x6 400d ($SD = 0.028 \text{ mm}^{-2}$, $V_s = 0.175\%$)
- Stitched 3x3 200d ($SD = 0.111 \text{ mm}^{-2}$, $V_s = 0.350\%$)

- Stitched 3x3 400d ($SD = 0.111 \text{ mm}^2$, $V_s = 0.700\%$)

V_s denotes stitch content. V_f of specimens ranges between 52.6- 54.3%. Thickness of specimens is around 4.1 mm.

2.2 Test specimen

The dimension of test specimen is 80 mm long and 15 mm wide. The specimen can be seen in Fig. 2. Test specimen is prepared by cutting the cured plate using water-cooled cutting machine AC-400CF. After cutting process, edges of the specimen are polished using abrasive rotating sandpapers with following roughness levels: rough (grit #500), moderately smooth (grit #1000) and very smooth (grit #1200). Gage area in compression test specimen is 10 mm long and 15 mm wide. Longitudinal and transverse strain gages (Kyowa) denoted as SG1 and SG2 are attached on front and back faces of specimen, respectively.

Fig. 2. Compression test specimen

2.3 Test fixture and procedures

NAL-II fixture is used in present compression test. It is selected because experimental results obtained utilizing NAL-II are reliable, repeatable and similar to those obtained by well-known standards of SRM-1 (SACMA) and ASTM D6641 (CLC) [14]. The

specimen size compatible with NAL-II is also relatively small. Another advantage of NAL-II is that the specimen does not require end-tabs since the fixture already provides metal supports that give sufficient clamping effect.

Fig. 3. (a) NAL-II compression test fixture, (b) pre-test alignment apparatus, (c) compression test setup

Fig. 3a shows NAL-II fixture, which consists of two main parts, namely the support and alignment collar. The support consisting of two components (Support-1, Support-2) is used to clamp the specimen at both ends, to provide base support, and to prevent brooming of specimen ends. In each support, four screws are used to clamp the specimen, specifically in gripping areas. After the specimen has been clamped, the alignment between Support-1 and Support-2 is checked. This alignment process is done by pre-test alignment apparatus shown in Fig. 3b. Before the pre-test alignment process, the screws are not heavily tightened to allow a smooth entrance into the alignment apparatus. When both supports have been aligned, screws are tightened within the alignment apparatus. Afterwards, specimen and the supports are taken out from pre-test alignment

apparatus, and inserted into the alignment collar. The collar contains two windows with rounded corners. These windows provide access for strain gage cables and for visual observation of specimen during compression test.

Compression test is carried out using Instron 4505 and its renewed system of 5500 with maximum load cell capacity of 100 kN. Test setup utilizing NAL-II fixture on Instron 4505 is shown Fig. 3c. Loading rate applied during compression test is 1 mm/min. Environment setting is set at room temperature of 20°C. Computer terminal is used to register load and displacement data. Stress is obtained by dividing the load with gross area of specimen (width x thickness). Strains are obtained from SG1 and SG2 strain gages. For each specimen type, three to five test samples are tested to obtain compressive strength.

2.4 Damage characterization procedures

Damage characterization was carried out by conducting interrupted test and optical microscopy on specially designed test specimens. The objectives are:

- to capture the damage process
- to have a comparative overview of damage mechanisms between unstitched and stitched composites under compression

One of the damage mechanisms in composites under compression is fiber kinking, which generally occurs in 0° fibers. Fiber kinking is generally triggered by initial fiber waviness and shear yield stress of matrix. In order to capture the development of fiber kinking and subsequent damage modes, a specially designed test specimen that clearly exhibits internal part of 0° tow (to capture fiber splitting and fiber kinking), resin-rich region and stitch thread is made to aid the damage observation. This test specimen is called *damage observation specimen*, and the process to produce such specimen is shown in Fig. 4a.

Fig. 4. (a) Process to produce damage observation specimen, (b) trimmed surface of gage area in damage observation specimen

To produce *damage observation specimen* the upper part of original compression test specimen is firstly trimmed in in-plane direction (x-y plane) up to a level whereby upper 0° tow is approximately cut into half. The trimming process is carried out using water-jet cutting machine (Maruto). After trimming process, two edges and front face of gage region are polished three times using abrasive rotating sandpapers starting from rough (grit #500), moderately smooth (grit #1000), and finally, very smooth (grit #1200). After polishing process, thickness of specimen that is originally around 4.1 mm becomes thinner. Thickness among damage observation specimens varies depending on the position of 0° tow relative to the back face of specimen that is between 3.1 to 3.4 mm. Fig. 4b

shows an example of front face of stitched specimen after trimming process that exhibits 0° tow, stitch threads and resin-rich region. Using such specimen, damages appeared in 0° tow, resin-rich region and stitch thread upon compression can be observed using microscope. However, it should be mentioned that by reducing the thickness of the specimen the maximum compressive load would be reduced. Thus, the maximum compressive load of *damage observation specimen* would be lower than that of compression test specimen. It is also noteworthy that *damage observation specimen* is non-symmetrical, which means that failure may initially occur in the front face of 0° tow.

Five samples are prepared for damage observation specimens representing five specimen types. *Damage observation specimen* is then inserted into NAL-II fixture. Interrupted test is carried out with loading rate of 0.5 mm/min. The test is periodically stopped at several load levels before final failure occurs. In each level, the specimen is taken out from the machine, and optical microscopy is performed on the specimen. Damages appeared in the front face and edges of the damage observation specimen are captured and noted.

3 Results and discussion

3.1 Compressive strength

Generally, compressive strength of stitched composites is relatively lower than that of unstitched composites. Average compressive strength of unstitched carbon/epoxy is 453 MPa, while that of stitched 6x6 200d, stitched 6x6 400d, stitched 3x3 200d and stitched 3x3 400d is 390 MPa, 395 MPa, 416 MPa and 408 MPa, respectively. Largest reduction of 13.9% is experienced by stitched 6x6 200d.

3.2 Failure mode

Failure of stitched and unstitched composites is catastrophic. The failure is characterized by the fracture of 0° tows, which is usually preceded by fiber kinking. Other failure modes also exist: delamination at the interfaces of ($0^\circ/-45^\circ$) and ($-45^\circ/0^\circ$); delamination adjacent to the fractured 0°

tows at specimen edge; matrix cracking in 90° , $+45^\circ$ and -45° tows (see Fig. 5).

Fig. 5. Failure characteristics under compression

Fig. 6. Fiber kinking in 0° tow (a) photomicrograph, (b) schematic

Fiber kinking may initiate at the location whereby maximum fiber waviness exists. Mechanism of fiber kinking in 3-D composite system has been described by Tong et al. [15]. Upon compressive loading, kinking will start to appear when the matrix around

misaligned fibers is undergoing plastic yielding. This matrix yielding allows a portion of fibers within 0° tow to rotate in parallel, which eventually causes fiber fracture over two planes. Characteristics of fiber kinking found in present experiment are shown in Fig. 6a, whereby a band of 0° fibers is broken. Schematic of fiber kinking drawn based on Fig. 6a is shown in Fig. 6b. Parameters in fiber kinking are identified as kink band width and kink angle. In Fig. 6b, kink band width is approximately $40\ \mu\text{m}$, whilst kink angle is 25° . The magnitude of kink band width may vary depending upon the thickness of fiber tow and the degree of waviness.

3.3 Damage mechanisms in unstitched composites

Damage progression in unstitched composites, as observed from front face of *damage observation specimen* is described in this section. Unstitched specimen used for damage observation has a thickness of 3.303 mm and width of 14.85 mm. Before the test is started, images of specimen are taken using optical microscope. The test is then carried out, and stopped at several stress levels: 249 MPa, 309 MPa, 363 MPa, 367 MPa, 388 MPa and 368 MPa (final failure). At each level, images of edges and front face are captured. Examples of image in unstitched composites under compression are shown in Fig. 7, specifically at 363 MPa, 367 MPa and 368 MPa (at failure).

At 363 MPa, several fiber splittings started to appear in 0° tow. No fiber kinking is visibly observed in the specimen at this stress level. This implies that fiber splitting is the earliest damage mode preceding the fiber kinking. When the load is increased to 367 MPa, the length of fiber splitting immediately increased reaching the boundary of clamping region (indicated by horizontal white marker). At the same time, fiber kinking rapidly develops across the width of specimen. Final failure occurs at 368 MPa.

In summary, the damage process in unstitched composites follows this sequence: fiber splitting \rightarrow delamination \rightarrow fiber kinking \rightarrow final failure (rupture of all fibers, fiber kinking, extensive delamination, shear fracture).

Fig. 7. Damage progression in unstitched composites (failure occurs at 368 MPa)

3.4 Damage mechanisms in stitched composites

For stitched composites (in this case, stitched 3x3), the test is stopped six times at several stress levels of 218 MPa, 260 MPa, 287 MPa, 299 MPa, 324 MPa and 323 MPa (final failure). Fig. 8 shows three examples of damage sequence in stitched composites at stress level of 260 MPa, 299 MPa and 323 MPa.

At 260 MPa, damage starts to appear in the form of resin cracking in the resin-rich regions. This resin cracking could be initiated by the voids in the resin-rich region. When the stress reaches 299 MPa, fiber splittings appear. Resin cracking and fiber splitting would interact with fiber kinking that spans across the width of 0° tows. At 323 MPa, specimen fails, and final failure is characterized by debonding of stitch threads from the surrounding matrix. Fracture of 0° tows also becomes very apparent, and collapse of overall specimen is inevitable. It is important to note that in stitched composites, the waviness around resin-rich region triggers the formation of resin cracking and fiber splitting, which eventually prompt the principal failure mode under compression, i.e. fiber kinking.

In summary, the damage process in stitched composites, follows this sequence: cracking in resin-rich region near stitch thread → fiber splitting → delamination → fiber kinking → final failure (rupture of all fibers, fiber kinking, extensive delamination, shear fracture, stitch debonding).

Fig. 8. Damage progression in stitched composites (failure occurs at 323 MPa)

3.5 A comparative overview of compressive failure in unstitched and stitched composites

A comparative overview based on the damage characterization is given in Fig. 9. This overview emphasizes that in stitched composites damage starts as early as 80% of σ_{uc} in the form of cracking in resin-rich region, which could be induced by the voids in resin-rich region and the interface between stitch thread and surrounding matrix. This crack induces fiber splitting, fiber kinking and delamination at 92% of σ_{uc} . Fiber splitting and fiber kinking develop near the flanks of resin-rich pocket due to the high shear stresses at the most 'wavy' part of 0° tows. In unstitched composites, the earliest damage was fiber splitting that occurred at later stage, i.e. 94% of σ_{uc} . After fiber splitting, fiber kinking and delamination develop in both unstitched and stitched composites, final failure ensues. Based on this overview, it is evident that the lower strength exhibited by the stitched composites is initiated by the cracking in resin-rich region that interacts with fiber splitting induced by the waviness of 0° tows, which is followed by fiber kinking and early catastrophic failure.

Fig. 9. A comparative overview of compressive failure in unstitched and stitched composites (σ_{uc} denotes ultimate compressive strength)

4 Conclusions

Experimental investigation was performed to study the effect of stitch density and stitch thread thickness on compressive strength and damage mechanisms in carbon/epoxy composites. Stitching generally reduces compressive strength of carbon/epoxy with maximum reduction of around 14%. Mechanism responsible for the lower compression strength in stitched composites is investigated by conducting interrupted test. The damage characterization reveals that in stitched composites damage initiates from resin-rich region at relatively lower compression stress. The damage may be generated from the void within the matrix, or debonding between stitch thread and surrounding matrix. When the crack is interacting with fiber splitting developed near the wavy fibers, fiber kinking rapidly grows and causes catastrophic failure in stitched composites. On the other hand, the earliest damage mode found in unstitched composites is fiber splitting, which occurs at later stage in comparison to cracking in resin-rich region of stitched composites. The fiber splitting is followed by the fiber kinking and collapse of the whole specimen. It is concluded that the compressive strength reduction stems from the existence of processing irregularities, i.e. resin-rich region. Therefore, minimizing the size of resin-rich region (e.g. by using smaller diameter yet stronger thread) may also helps to improve or maintain compressive strength of stitched composites.

Acknowledgements

This research is funded by the Tokyo Metropolitan Government from the project of Asian Network of Major Cities 21 (ANMC21).

References

- [1] KT. Tan, N. Watanabe and Y. Iwahori "Effect of stitch density and stitch thread thickness on low-velocity impact damage of stitched composites". *Compos Part A*, Vol. 41, No. 12, pp 1857-1868, 2010.
- [2] A. Yudhanto, N. Watanabe, Y. Iwahori, H. Hoshi. "Effect of stitch density on tensile properties and damage mechanisms of stitched carbon/epoxy composites", *Compos Part B*, Vol. 46, pp 151-165, 2013.

- [3] M.B. Dow, D.L. Smith. "Damage-tolerant composite materials produced by stitching carbon fabrics". *Proceedings of 21st international SAMPE technical conference*, September 1989.
- [4] X. Du, F. Xue, Z. Gu. "Experimental study of the effect of stitching on strength of a composite laminate". *Proceedings of international symposium on composite materials and structures*, Beijing, PR China, 10-13 June 1986.
- [5] H. Harris, N. Schinske, R. Krueger, B. Swanson. "Multiaxial stitched preform reinforcement for RTM fabrication". *Proceedings of 36th international SAMPE technical conference*, California, USA, 15-18 April 1991.
- [6] I. Herszberg, M.K. Bannister. "Compression and compression-after-impact properties of thin stitched carbon/epoxy composites". *Proceedings of 5th Australia aeronautical conference*, Melbourne, Australia, 20-23 March 1993.
- [7] S. Adanur, S.R. Gongalareddy. "Compressive properties of stitched woven fiberglass fabric reinforced composite sections for civil engineering applications". *Proceedings of 3rd international conference on composite engineering (ICCE-3)*, New Orleans, USA, 21-26 July 1996.
- [8] H. Hesz, N. Himmel. "Structurally stitched NCF CFRP laminates. Part 1: Experimental characterization of in-plane and out-of-plane properties". *Compos Sci Technol* 2011;71:549-568.
- [9] A.P. Mouritz, B.N. Cox. "A mechanistic approach to the properties of stitched laminates". *Compos: Part A* 2000;31(1):1-27.
- [10] A.P. Mouritz, K.H. Leong, I. Herszberg. "A review of the effect of stitching on the in-plane mechanical properties of fibre-reinforced polymer composites". *Compos: Part A* 1997;28A(12):979-991.
- [11] J.R. Reeder. "Comparison of the compressive strengths for stitched and toughened composite systems". *Technical report*, NASA/TM-109108, 1994.
- [12] M.T. Cholakara, B.Z. Jang, C.Z. Wang. "Deformation and failure mechanisms in 3D composites". *Proceedings of 34th international SAMPE symposium*, Nevada, USA, 8-11 May 1989.
- [13] G.L. Farley. "A mechanism responsible for reducing compression strength of through-the-thickness reinforced composite materials". *J Compos Mater* 1992;26:1784-1795.
- [14] T. Ogasawara, T. Ishikawa. "Evaluation of standard compressive test methods for carbon fiber composites and proposal of a simple test method (NAL-II)". *Technical report*, JAXA-RM-08-010, 2009 (in Japanese).
- [15] L. Tong, A.P. Mouritz, M.K. Bannister. "3D fibre reinforced polymer composites". Elsevier Science, 2002.